

Introduction of Palmyra Palm fiber as an Alternative Natural Fiber in Textile Industry

MT Rasnatun Ferdous^{1*}, Eaty Rani Halder¹, Dr Lu Jianjun¹

¹Department of Textile engineering & Textile Design, Shanxi , China

Accepted December 11,2021
Published December 17,2021

*Corresponding Author:
MT Rasnatun Ferdous,

DOI :<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5789789>

Pages: 48-57

Funding: N/A

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):
Ferdous, M. R., Halder, E. R., & Dr. Jianjun, L. (2021). Introduction of Palmyra Palm Fiber as an Alternative Natural Fiber in Textile Industry. *North American Academic Research*, 4(12), 48-57. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5789789>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, natural products are extremely preferred among the people. These natural products are produced by environment friendly sources. In case of textiles, bast fibers play significant role in producing natural products that are extracted from the stem of various plant and environment friendly in nature. The bast fibers can also improve the livelihood of the poor farmers who are involved in the cultivation of the plants and extraction and processing of the fibers. Palm fibre is one of the bast fiber which is a waste product from the fruit crushing-extracting process in local communities. Nonetheless, yarn is unique in its characteristic pattern and is stronger than cotton. The aim of this study is to introducing of palm fiber and some basic comparisons with other fibers (cotton, polyester, wool, viscose, silk), where palm fiber shows significant results. Results showed that, the strength percentage of palm fiber (4.2%) is less than polyester (6%) but more than cotton (4.1%). At the same way, the percentage of elongation shows for palm fiber as (21%) and cotton viscose, polyester shows (10% ,(13%), (30%) respectively. For moisture regain palm fiber shows remarkable performance with (13.25%) which is the highest one.

Keywords: SCOURING & BLEACHING, ACID DYE, BASIC DYE, REACTIVE DYE, SULPHUR DYE

Introduction

World is as of now concentrating on alternate material sources that are environment agreeable and biodegradable in nature. Because of the expanding natural concerns, bio composite produced out of regular fiber and polymeric resin, is one of the late advancements in the business and constitutes the present extent of experimental work. People are demanding more natural product even in garment and fashion sector. It is 100% biodegradable and compostable, and has the ability to naturally degrade into its basic constituents and return back into the environment. In the 1980s the shift from natural fibers to manmade fibres was mainly to bridge the gap between the increasing demand for textile fibres and the limited supply of natural fibres. In order to reverse this shift, there is a need to explore more sources of natural fibres and increase the

biodiversity of fibre crops. The yarn is unique in its characteristic pattern and is stronger than cotton. When woven, the fabric is high in drapability like linen, lighter than cotton, rich in lustered, and characterized by the unique palm fibre pattern. Most importantly, the process makes use of locally available waste products to create value added products through an eco-friendly production process. The researchers are optimistic that this further study may offer a practical means of improving the quality of local textiles and will provide new alternatives for the selection of yarns from natural fibres to produce local textile products. It may also offer opportunities for larger-scale commercial production for domestic consumption and the export trade. The study findings may provide the basis for production of innovative handmade and industrial textiles which are environmentally friendly. The objectives of this research are: (1) to improve and develop preparation processes of the palm fibre as a suitable raw material in the production of yarns; (2) to create alternative yarn colors using natural dyes. Natural fiber like Palmyra palm fiber provides new hope for researchers with its excellent chemical and physical properties. This work investigates the Palmyra palm fiber from extraction to dyeing and characterizes its chemical and physical properties. Also compare results with other fibers.

Materials and method

Materials: Palm fibre; comber; yarn winder.

Chemicals: Reactive dyes, basic dyes, salt, acetic acid, sodium acetate, soda ash, stabilizer, hydrogen Peroxide, wetting agent, sequestering agent, leveling agent

2.1 Palm fruit Fiber extraction:

At first the ripe fruits are collected. Then the blackish husk is removed. And fruit protein parts are removed properly in pond water. Then the seeds are dried by sunshine

Figure 2.1: Raw fiber

The seeds are separated from each other with fiber. The fibers from the seeds are collected with a sharp blade which contains yellowish color. Then the fibers are washed off by detergent with water. Then the washed fiber is boiled with normal water and soda at a temperature of 50°C to remove gum like material from the

fiber and then treated with acetic acid to neutralize the effect of caustic soda. Finally dry in the sun. About 30g fiber can be collected from a fruit by hand.

The seeds are separated from each other with fiber. The fibers from the seeds are collected with a sharp blade which contains yellowish color. Then the fibers are washed off by detergent with water. Then the washed fiber is boiled with normal water and soda at a temperature of 50°C to remove gum like material from the fiber and then treated with acetic acid to neutralize the effect of caustic soda. Finally dry in the sun. About 30g fiber can be collected from a fruit by hand.

2.2 Scouring and bleaching:

Recipe:

Hydrogen peroxide	4 g/L
Stabilizer	1 g/L
Sodium hydroxide	3 g/L
Wetting agent	1 g/L
Sequestering agent	1 g/L
Temperature	100°C
Time	30 min
PH	10.5-11.0
M: L	1: 40

Figure 2.2: scoured & bleached fiber

Result: The scoured and bleached fibers are shown better whiteness. And it shows softer appearance than raw fiber.

3. Dyeing:

The Palmyra palm fruit fiber can be dyed with Reactive and Basic dyes. But it is highly qualified for basic dyes. This fiber contains small amount of cellulose. Cellulose has no acidic group and therefore no affinity to basic dyes. And hydroxyl group of cellulose are oxidized and form oxy-cellulose. Then there treat with basic days. And the basic dye is highly active with this condition.

3.1 Dyeing with Reactive dye:

At first 5g of fiber is taken. Then the fiber is dyed with following recipe

Recipe:

Dye	2%
NaCl	20g/L
Soda ash	5g/L
Wetting agent	1g/L
Sequestering agent	1g/L
Temperature	80°C
Time	30min
PH	10.5
M: L	1:20

After that soaping is done with the following recipe

Soaping chemical	4g/L
Temperature	80°C
Time	10min [3]

Figure 3.1: Dyed fiber with reactive dye

3.2 Dyeing with basic dye

At first 5g of fiber was taken. Then it was dyed with the following recipe

Recipe:

Basic dye	2%
Sodium acetate	1.5g/L
Acetic acid	1g/L
Wetting agent	1g/L
Sequestering agent	1g/L
Temperature	80°C
Time	30min
M: L	1:20

First the solution is prepared, then the steam is on and process is run as before, we checked the ph and the entire dyeing procedure carefully. Drained the water from bath, then the dyed fiber is washed with hot water for 10 minutes at 90°C. After that the fiber is dried and it can be said that the dye take up% is very good.

Figure 3.2: Dyed fiber with Basic dye

3.3 Comparison palm fiber with other dyes:

- 3.3.1 Direct dye

This dyes are generally sodium salt of sulphonic acid .They have direct affinity to cellulosic fiber. This dyes has poor fastness to wash. As palm fiber have low quantity of cellulose and wash fastness is very poor of this dyes. So palm fiber isn't suitable for dyeing with direct dyes.

- 3.3.2 Acid dye

Acid dyes are water soluble. They have direct affinity to wool silk & nylon. They have no affinity to cellulosic fiber. Since palm fiber contain a low amount of cellulose, so it is not suitable for dyeing with acid dyes.

- 3.3.3 Sulphur dye

These dyes are complex organic compounds containing Sulphur. They are insoluble in water but soluble under reduce condition. They are applied on cotton for cheaper shades. They have high wet fastness but poor light fastness during dyeing fabric. As these dyes are water insoluble & their light fastness is poor, so palm fiber is not suitable for dyeing with Sulphur dyes.

4. Results and Discussion

Measuring Scale

	Excellent		Good		Poor	
Category	Reactive	Basic	Direct	Acid	Sulphur	
Color fastness	Good	Excellent	Poor	Poor	Good	
Affinity to fiber	Good	Excellent	Poor	Poor	Poor	

4.2 Comparison with other fibers:

4.2.1 Strength:

Chart: Comparison of strength of different fiber

From figure it is seen that strength of palm fiber is about 4.2 g/den which is only below the polyester among all those fiber. [3]

4.2.2 Elongation%:

Chart: Comparison of elongation% of different fiber

From figure it is seen that elongation % of palm fiber is more than cotton and viscose. [3]

4.3.3 Moisture Regain%:

Chart: Comparison of moisture regain% of different fiber

It is seen that moisture regain percentage of palm fiber is more among all the fiber in the chart except wool. Palmyra palm fruit fiber is long staple fiber. The fiber without blending with cotton cannot be processed with the machinery which is developed only for cotton fiber processing. It is not possible to make yarn by using only this fiber in ring spinning frame as well as open end spinning frame. But after blending with 60% raw cotton it is possible to make both ring yarn and rotor yarn. It can be stated that by visual estimation the uniformity of yarn in both ring and rotor is comparatively poor. It happened because drawing and doubling is carried out in same machine and doubling is done by using only four ply of drawn sliver. The ring yarn is normally finer than rotor yarn. But table2 shows that, the count of ring yarn is 7Ne and count of rotor yarn is 10Ne though both the yarn is produced from the same sliver. This is happened because of producing ring yarn directly from sliver. Table 3 and table 4 show that breaking strength of rotor yarn and ring yarn 327.0c N/tex and 400.0c N/tex respectively. The breaking strength in both cases is relatively good. The strength can be increased by changing TPI and other parameters. The strength of yarn is comparatively low because of using low quality cotton in blending. By blending uniformly with high quality cotton fiber and use of synthetic fiber in blending desired strength of yarn can be obtained. The elongation % of ring yarn is 6.81 which are nearer to elongation percentage 6.83% of 40 tex jute cotton blended yarn where cotton is 80% and jute is 40%. The yarn can be widely used inn heavy fabric, fancy items, decorative purpose, non-woven, geo-textiles etc. [3]

Palmyra palm fruit fiber Chemical composition comparison with cotton, silk, jute:

Name	Palmyra Palm	Cotton	Sisal	Jute
Cellulose	37.01	94	71.5	65.2
Holocellulose	68.52	0	0	0
Lignin	18.57	0	6	10.8
Ash	0.64	1.2	0	0
Pentosan	28.51	0	0	0

Conclusion

Palmyra palm yields are natural, uneven-sized fiber. The prime objective of this study is to explore the

potential use of Borassusfruit fibers in textile. The properties of fiber are determined. The fiber shows a good dye take up rate, strength, elongation and moisture regain percentage. The fiber cannot be processed alone in cotton processing machine but by blending with cotton both ring and rotor yarn can be produced. The strength of yarn in both cases is relatively good .The strength of yarn depends on various parameters. By changing these parameters increase of strength is possible. The palm fiber can be used effectively instead of synthetic fiber which (synthetic) causes environmental pollution severely. This fiber can be an important source of non-woven textiles where strength is crying needs. By surface modification the fiber can be used alone without blending. In summary, the fiber can be used in geotextiles as well as in other reinforcing textile materials and in different value added items.

References

1. Janick J & Robert E Paull . The Encyclopedia of Fruit and Nut. 4th ed. London: cabi publication. 9. (2008)
2. Kabir H. Forestry and Environmental Science, Shahajalal University of Science and Technology, Sylhet. Available: <http://forestrysust.blogspot.com/2008/12/palm-tree-in-bangladesh.html>. Last accessed 21st March 2017. (2008)
3. Park J. Palm fruit Fiber extraction, spinning, dyeing, and characterization. Available: <http://www.textiletoday.com.bd/palm-fruit-fiber-extraction-spinning-dyeing-and-characterization/>. Last accessed 20st March 2017. (June 1, 2014).
4. Morton, J.F. The Palmyra or Toddy Palm (*Borassusflabellifer* L.). Available: <http://www.fao.org/livestock/agap/frg/ECONF95/HTML/TODDY.HTM>. Last accessed 21 march, 2017. (Dec 2011).
5. Paul R. Toddy Palm - Sugar Palm (Palmyra Palm): This can be a Billion Dollar Industry if proper attention is given by the Industry, Scientists and Researchers. Available: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/toddy-palm-sugar-palmpalmyra-can-billion-dollar-industry-osk-reddy>. Last accessed 15th March 2017(April 30, 2016).
6. Srinivasa babu N . Manufacturing and Characterization of Long Palmyra Palm/*BorassusFlabellifer* Petiole Fibre Reinforced Polyester Composites. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212017314000693>. Last accessed 20th March, 2017. (2014)
7. WaranyouSridach. Pulping and paper properties of Palmyra palm fruit fibers. Pulping and paper properties of Palmyra palm fruit fibers. 11 (1), 203. (Mar. - Apr. 2010).
8. Fatma T. Surface Modification of Bast-Based Natural Fibers through Environment Friendly Methods, Generation, Development and Modifications of Natural Fibers, Mudassar Abbas and Han-Yong Jeon, IntechOpen, DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.85693. Available from: <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/69732> (October 24th 2019).
9. Soiraya, B., Chooseng, K., and Siripun, A.,. The Development of Plam fibre products to Industry Thailand Textile Institute, Bangkok. (Thai) (2007)
10. Ujjin, S.,Chollakup, R. and Pasukdee, W.,. Pilot project of pineapple leaf utilization for textile industry. Physical properties of pineapple/cotton blended yarns and fabrics. The Thailand Research Fund. Bangkok. (Thai) (2003)
11. Upan, P., and Chumsang, C.,. The Development of Palm Fibres products to Textile Industry. Thailand Textile Institute, Bangkok. (Thai)(2010)

MT Rasnatun Ferdous
MSc in Textile Engineering
Taiyuan University of Technology
Shanxi, China

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

